

That Man...Pauling! (continued)

After reading the commentaries on his book, *Vitamin C and the Common Cold*, published in our January/February issue, Dr. Pauling expressed a desire to respond to these criticisms. We are pleased to publish his comment and also one from a distinguished clinician, Dr. Charles E. Butterworth.

I have read with pleasure the comments on my book, *Vitamin C and the Common Cold*, made by four distinguished authorities in the fields of medicine and nutrition.

One point raised by them, as well as by others, seems to me to deserve detailed discussion. This is the question whether the weight of evidence of the controlled experiments that have been carried out shows vitamin C to be effective in preventing and mitigating the common cold, or shows it not to be effective. In my book I discussed all of the controlled experiments known to me, and concluded that they show with high statistical significance that even rather small daily amounts of ingested vitamin C, 200 mg to 1,000 mg, are effective in decreasing the incidence and severity of the common cold in subjects under normal exposure to virus infections. Many people, even after reading my book, have expressed the opposite opinion, although sometimes with a qualification such as to introduce the factor of personal judgment.

ADJECTIVE QUALIFIED

For example, Professor Passmore refers to two studies discussed by me, those of Cowan, Diehl, and Baker and of Glazebrook and Thomson, both published in 1942, in which decreases of 15 percent and 17 percent, respectively, were observed in the incidence of colds in the group of subjects receiving 200 mg per day of ascorbic acid, relative to the other subjects, and makes the following statement: "I have re-read the original accounts of these trials carefully. Pauling's comments, while factual and accurate, seem in no way to invalidate the original interpretation of both trials by the authors, which was that the ascorbic acid had no practical effect."

I shall point out that the results reported by these investigators, as well as by some others, have high statistical significance. Professor Passmore does not contradict this statement—he does not conclude, nor did the authors

themselves conclude, that ascorbic acid had no effect; instead, he and the original authors concluded that ascorbic acid had no "practical" effect. It is a matter of judgment as to whether a 15-percent or 17-percent decrease in the incidence of colds is a practical effect, and it is my judgment, as expressed in my book, that it is.

ADJECTIVE UNQUALIFIED

Professor Stare states, "Pauling's book does not contain acceptable scientific evidence with appropriate controls to support his testimonials, or those of others, that vitamin C will actually deter or mitigate the common cold."

This statement differs from the statement by Professor Passmore, in that it does not include any qualifying adjective. Professor Stare's statement is not correct.

Professor Stare's comment, made elsewhere, that "This view is held by the vast majority of physicians, nutritionists, or researchers dealing with viruses and the particular viruses known to be involved with some colds," is in my opinion irrelevant. Scientific truth is not reliably determined by a majority vote. In 1775, Lavoisier presented the evidence to support the idea that combustion involves the combination of the combustible material with oxygen. For some years after 1775 the majority opinion of chemists continued to be that combustion involved the liberation of phlogiston; but the phlogiston theory was wrong, despite this majority opinion.

Dr. Charles C. Edwards, Food and Drug Commissioner, is quoted in news dispatches as having made the following statement: "There is no scientific evidence and never have been any meaningful studies indicating that vitamin C is capable of preventing or curing colds."

Here Dr. Edwards, apparently ignoring the analysis of the evidence presented in my book, has made an un-

qualified statement that contradicts the facts.

Dr. Philip L. White, Secretary of the Council on Foods and Nutrition of the American Medical Association, made the following statement in his article in *Today's Health* for November 1970: "Unfortunately, it is still a widespread belief that extra ascorbic acid can not only prevent colds but also lessen the severity and duration of colds and other respiratory infections. Even when consumed at the first sign of a sniffle, large doses of the vitamin are useless." I believe that the evidence does not support this statement.

In my book I described my analysis of the published studies and reached two conclusions: First, that the regular daily ingestion of a supplementary amount of the important food ascorbic acid results in a decrease of the number of colds, indicated by the evidence to be about 15 percent for an intake of 200 mg per day and about 60 percent for an intake of 1,000 mg per day; and second, that the ingestion of ascorbic acid in amounts 500 mg per hour or more, beginning at the first indication of a cold, ameliorates the cold.

RESULTS SIGNIFICANT

I shall discuss in some detail the published studies supporting the first conclusion, beginning with the 1942 paper by Cowan, Diehl, and Baker.

Cowan, Diehl, and Baker reported the results of a study carried out with nearly 400 students of the University of Minnesota, during a period of 28 weeks. The subjects were students who volunteered to participate in the study because they were particularly susceptible to colds. Persons whose difficulties seemed to be due primarily to chronic sinusitis or allergic rhinitis were excluded from the study. The students were assigned alternately and without selection to an experimental group and a control group, and were kept ignorant of the treatment they were receiving. The students in the control group were treated exactly

like those in the experimental group, except that they received placebos instead of the vitamin.

This investigation seems to have been carried out with great care. The investigators were able and well-trained physicians. Dr. Diehl was at that time and for many years later Dean of Medical Sciences in the University of Minnesota. I have not seen any serious published criticism of their work.

They reported the average number of colds for the 208 subjects who received 200 mg of vitamin C per day to be 1.9 ± 0.07 , and that for the 155 students in the control group to be 2.2 ± 0.08 , the difference being given by the investigators as 0.3 ± 0.11 . It is unfortunate that they did not report the average number of colds to one more significant figure. In the text they state that "The actual difference between the two groups during the period of the study amounts to one-third of a cold per person."

In the statistical analysis of these observations I take as the null hypothesis that the two groups are selected from the same population, and as the alternative hypothesis that the group receiving ascorbic acid had some degree of protection against the common cold. The difference 0.30 in the average number of colds leads, by the student's t-test, one-tailed, to P equal to or less than 0.004. Accordingly, the observed difference has high statistical significance; the null hypothesis, that ascorbic acid has no effect, is rejected at the 99.6 percent confidence level.

Cowan, Diehl, and Baker state: "Statistical analysis of the data reveals that a difference as large as this would arise only three or four times in a hundred through chance alone. One may therefore consider this as probably a significant difference, and vitamin C supplement to the diet may therefore be judged to give a slight advantage in reducing the number of colds experienced." I have not found any statistical treatment leading to a value of P as large as 0.03, and I think that this statement was a very conservative one.

It cannot be denied that the careful study carried out by Cowan, Diehl, and Baker produced statistically significant evidence for an effect of ascorbic acid in decreasing the incidence of the common cold. In the text of

their article the authors state, "However, one may well question the practical importance of such a difference." They express no doubt about having observed a statistically significant effect, and I can only assume that it was because of their feeling that this effect was not of practical significance that they misrepresented their results in their summary, which consisted of the following single sentence: "This controlled study yields no indication that either large doses of vitamin C alone or large doses of vitamins A, B₁, B₂, C, and D and nicotinic acid have any important effect on the number or severity of infections of the upper respiratory tract when administered to young adults who presumably are already on a reasonably adequate diet."

Cowan, Diehl, and Baker also reported that the average number of days lost from school per person in the ascorbic-acid group was 1.1, which is 31 percent less than the value for the control group, 1.6. These values are, of course, not uncorrelated with the average number of colds. However, the severity of the individual cold, as measured by the number of days lost per cold, might be considered to be essentially uncorrelated. The average number of days lost per cold is 0.73 for the control group and 0.58 for the vitamin-C group—20 percent less. The probability of such a difference in severity in the colds is found by the chi-square test to be P equal to or less than 0.001. Accordingly we may conclude that the severity of the individual colds had a statistically significant difference.

From these considerations we are led to the conclusion that ascorbic acid was found by Cowan, Diehl, and Baker to be significantly effective both in decreasing the number of colds and in decreasing their severity. The statement made by the investigators in their summary, that their controlled study yielded no indication that vitamin C has any important effect on the number or severity of infections of the upper respiratory tract, is misleading, and would be false if the adjective "important" were omitted.

I shall not discuss the more complicated and less carefully controlled study by Glazebrook and Thomson, except to say that they also observed about the same decrease in the number of colds in the ascorbic-acid group,

and that their results are compatible with those of Cowan, Diehl, and Baker.

CONCLUSIONS UNCONTRADICTED

In my search of the literature I have not found a single-blind or double-blind study that contradicts, with statistical significance (P less than 0.05), my conclusion that the regular ingestion of 200 mg of ascorbic acid per day leads to about 15 percent decrease in the incidence and in the severity of colds in subjects exposed to viruses in the normal way. On the contrary: several investigations support this conclusion, with statistical significance.

The best study that has been carried out with administration of a larger amount of ascorbic acid, 1,000 mg per day, is that by Dr. Guenther Ritzel, of the Medical Service of the Schools of the Canton of Basel, Switzerland. This study was published in *Helvetica Medica Acta* **28**: 63 (1961). It involved 179 skiers, who were free of symptoms of colds at the beginning of the study. It was a double-blind study, with neither the subjects nor the physicians having knowledge of which subjects received ascorbic acid and which received the placebo tablets. The tablets, both ascorbic acid and placebo, were prepared by the firm of Hoffmann-LaRoche and Company, Basel, and were in the original packages labeled with consecutive numbers. The physicians verified that the tablets were swallowed by the subjects, and that there was no opportunity for them to interchange tablets. Each subject was examined every day, by questioning, temperature measurements, inspection of the throat and nose, auscultation of the lungs, and so on. The principal symptoms of the common cold that were evaluated were laryngitis, tonsillitis, sore throat, bronchitis and coughing, fever and chills, rhinitis, otitis and earache, and herpes labialis. The authors stated (my translation), "The group of subjects treated with vitamin C showed a reduction in the number of days of illness to 39 percent and in the number of individual symptoms to 35 percent of the values for the placebo group. The statistical evaluation by use of the 2×2 contingency table gives a significant difference (0.001 < P < 0.01)." Moreover,

the author states, "In this connection it appeared to us that an evaluation of the results from the therapeutic side would also be interesting. For that purpose we have compared the mean length of the period of illness for the two groups. It amounted to 1.8 days per cold for the vitamin-C group, and 2.6 days per cold for the patients who received placebos. These averages are also significantly different from one another (P less than 0.05; t-distribution)."

I have verified the calculations of the statistical significance of these results, and have also made another calculation. From the numbers given in the paper it can be calculated that 17 of the 139 subjects who received vitamin C caught colds during the period of study, and 31 of the 140 subjects who received the placebo did. This difference is statistically significant (0.02 less than P, less than 0.01 on a one-tailed test, null hypothesis the same effect of ascorbic acid and placebo, alternative hypothesis a protective effect of ascorbic acid greater than for the placebo). My conclusion is that this careful double-blind test shows that 1,000 mg per day of ascorbic acid has the statistically significant effect both of decreasing the number of colds and of decreasing the severity of individual colds.

Dr. Ritzel added a summary in the English language to his paper, as follows: "The possibility of preventing infection by administration of vitamin C was investigated in a moderately large test population during a period of increased exposure. The trial was conducted in such a way as to exclude sources of error in assessing subjective symptoms. Statistical evaluation of the results confirmed the efficacy of vitamin C in the prophylaxis and treatment of colds. Problems of therapeutic trials with pluripotential preparations which have to be judged chiefly on the basis of subjective symptoms are discussed."

There was a serious error in the report of the results of this investigation in an editorial article in *Nutrition Reviews* 25: 228 (1967). The statement in the editorial article is, "G. Ritzel *Helvetica Med. Acta* 28: 63 (1961), in a study of 279 skiers, allocated by alternate numbers to groups receiving 1,000 mg ascorbic acid daily or identical inert placebo, reported a reduction of 39 percent in the number

of days ill from upper respiratory tract infections and a reduction of 35 percent in the incidence of individual symptoms in the supplemented group as compared with the placebo group. A slight reduction in the mean duration of illness from 2.6 in the control series to 1.8 days in the treated series was noted. In this study, the assessment was largely based on subjective reports from the participants and only limited clinical observations were made."

In fact, Dr. Ritzel reported a reduction of 61 percent, not 39 percent, in the number of days ill from upper respiratory tract infections and a reduction of 65 percent, not 35 percent, in the incidence of individual symptoms. This sort of carelessness by the editors of *Nutrition Reviews* suggests that they were not making a serious effort to analyze the existing evidence about the value of ascorbic acid in preventing and ameliorating colds. Moreover, bias is indicated by the reference to a "slight" reduction in the mean duration of illness from 2.6 in the control series to 1.8 days in the treated series; this reduction is by 31 percent, and it is statistically significant.

The various other reports of studies showing some protective effect of ascorbic acid are, in my opinion, less significant than the report of Cowan, Diehl, and Baker and that of Ritzel.

STATEMENTS IMPROPER

It is my opinion that it is not proper for Professor Stare to have made the statement, "Pauling's book does not contain acceptable scientific evidence with appropriate controls to support his testimonials, or those of others, that vitamin C will actually deter or mitigate the common cold." My book contains a discussion of the work of Cowan, Diehl, and Baker and the work of Ritzel, similar to that given above, but a little shorter, and of several other investigations. Until someone has provided evidence to invalidate these studies, statements contradicting the statistically significant results that these physicians reported must be described as irresponsible.

The work of Walker, Bynoe, and Tyrrell, *British Medical Journal* 1: 603 (1967), has been quoted as providing evidence against the thesis that ascorbic acid has protective value. They reported a decrease of only 6 percent

in the incidence of colds in the subjects who received three grams of ascorbic acid per day, relative to those who received a placebo. This result is not statistically significant; the decrease would have had to be by 40 percent or more to be statistically significant with the number of subjects studied. Three days after the treatment began, the subjects were challenged by being given intranasal drops containing one or another of five viruses. Under these unusual conditions of exposure to the virus, no large protective effect of ascorbic acid was observed. How much relevance this study has to the question of protection against the common cold under normal conditions of exposure to virus infection is uncertain.

Professor Stare expresses doubt that a sustained level greater than 1.39 mg per 100 ml can be achieved in the serum by an increased intake of ascorbic acid. We have verified that it can be; for example, the regular intake, in hourly doses, of 40 mg per kilogram body weight per day, leads to a sustained level in the serum of 3 mg per 100 ml, which is five times the value obtained by regular ingestion of one-fifth the amount. The serum level continues to rise with further increase in the rate of ingestion of ascorbic acid.

Professor Passmore has stated that there is no epidemiological support for the claim that ascorbic acid has value in providing protection against the common cold. He mentions the difference in the recommended daily allowance of 60 mg for Americans and 30 in Britain, and states that in India and Pakistan most people would have intakes of 15 mg per day or less, and then states that it is his impression that Americans have more numerous and severe colds than do the British, Indians, or Pakistanis. I reply by pointing out that Cowan, Diehl, and Baker have reported a 15-percent decrease in incidence of colds after ingestion of 200 mg per day. The difference between 60 mg per day (Americans) and the smaller amounts mentioned above would be expected, on the basis of an assumed linear relationship, to cause Americans to have about three percent fewer colds than people in Britain, and five percent fewer than people in Pakistan and India. These differences are, of course, too small to be detected except by

careful study of a large number of subjects; and, moreover, other differences between life on different continents might have an influence.

PASSMORE'S PALLIATIVE

I may mention two minor points. Professor Passmore has said that my claim is not supported by any theoretical concept of how the vitamin might work at the molecular level. In fact, this matter is discussed on page 38 of my book, where I suggest that the effectiveness of ascorbic acid in providing protection against virus

diseases might result from its function in the synthesis and activity of interferon in preventing the entry of virus particles into the cells. He also says that my chapter on orthomolecular medicine has no mention of vitamin C and the common cold. The last paragraph of this chapter reads as follows: "A large rate of intake of ascorbic acid is required for optimal protection against infectious disease. The use of ascorbic acid to provide protection against the common cold, influenza, rheumatic fever, pneumonia, and other infectious diseases may well be the most important of all methods of

orthomolecular medicine." I may add that the role of viruses in producing cancer might have justified my including cancer in this list.

There is in the medical literature some sound evidence, obtained in studies made by responsible physicians, that ascorbic acid has some value in decreasing the incidence and severity of the common cold. How great this value is remains uncertain. I may mention that I do not have strong objections to the treatment referred to by Professor Passmore, the ingestion of Scotch whisky, but I advocate trying ascorbic acid as well.

Dr. Charles E. Butterworth

Comments

Dr. Butterworth is Professor of Medicine at the University of Alabama in Birmingham. He is a member of the Council on Foods and Nutrition of the American Medical Association and Secretary-Treasurer of the American Society for Clinical Nutrition.

Three cheers for your objective appraisal of Pauling's book set forth in the editorial "The Virtue of Theory" (NUTRITION TODAY, Jan.-Feb., 1971). Of all the views I have seen and heard, including those which accompany it in the same issue, yours comes nearest to expressing my own. I think it is extremely important to look beyond the petty issues of what we know, or think we know, as nutrition scientists. It is personally distressing to see distinguished nutritionists rise up in haughty grandeur and react as Dr. Stare has done (on page 20) saying, "Like Hansel and Gretel, he (Pauling) is lost in the woods—of health and nutrition, areas outside his competence." It is all too easy to take this approach, and to withdraw behind a facade of complacency and omniscience. It takes courage, on the other hand, to accept Pauling's challenges and to look beyond one's personal involvement and commitments. I suspect that Pauling has done better in his foray into the field of nutrition than most nutritionists could have done in, say, physical chemistry.

It seems to me that there may be a sound basis in biochemical knowledge, by which larger intakes of ascorbic acid just might be beneficial in the prevention of colds, and possibly of certain degenerative disorders of other tissues. It is pertinent to call attention (for example) to the presence of L-iduronic acid in mucopolysaccharides such as the sulfated proteoglycans of skin, arteries, and heparin-like compounds. In view of its unique L-con-

figuration, it is readily conceivable that L-iduronic acid may be derived from ascorbate.

In another area, some of our comfortable concepts about immunity to viral disease have recently been dealt a shattering blow by the work of Kozloff and his colleagues. These workers have shown that certain phage virus particles are rendered non-infective by treatment with "conjugase." This naturally occurring enzyme shortens the polyglutamate side chain of folic acid and is thought to be induced by folic-acid feeding. Thus, certain revisions are needed in the orthodox concept that immunity requires the production of a specific immune globulin in response to prior exposure to a pathogen.

It has been argued that the urinary excretion of unaltered ascorbate after ingestion of large doses is an indication of a lack of need. This view does not take into account the possibility of secondary metabolic events in the process of absorption, transit, and excretion, for example enzyme induction.

If one should set aside, for the moment, the entire controversial topic of whether vitamin C prevents the common cold, there remains in Pauling's book a wealth of sound nutritional thought. In the book, Pauling does the following:

1. Favors direct analysis of foods and food composition.
2. Favors better analysis of eating habits (current and ancestral).
3. Considers evolutionary biochemistry in relation to nutritional needs.

4. Emphasizes the dangers and financial expense of current drug practices and self-medication.

5. Challenges the criteria used for determining nutritional adequacy.

6. Makes a strong plea for improved nutrition research and education.

7. Challenges the interest of physicians in the welfare of patients.

I believe most people who profess an interest in clinical nutrition would find themselves in agreement with most of the above viewpoints. The last point is the most difficult to accept and to assess. I suggest that it should at least be brought into the open for consideration, to discover if the allegation has merit. There is nothing to be lost in the process.

I feel strongly that it would be a terrible mistake if the "Nutrition Community" reacted negatively to this book, when a positive, constructive response would be equally justifiable and would move us closer to the goals that many of us seek in common. One is haunted by the specter of the British admiralty waiting 50 years to eliminate scurvy from their Navy—and 100 years to eliminate it from the merchant fleet. It seems to me that this kindly man is chiding the entire medical profession and all nutrition scientists, and suggesting that they look to their laurels. I believe the proper response should be, "Perhaps you are right, Dr. Pauling. We welcome your interest in nutrition, your effort and your suggestions. Let us look into the situation more thoroughly."